

Supplementary Material

1. Final damage parameter values

Parameter	Numerical value
Loss of capital stock due to sea-level rise (%)	at 2°C: 1% in 10 years, at 3°C: loss of 1.5 % in 10 years; at 4 °C: loss of 2% of global capital stock in 10 years
Sectoral shares of damages in capital stock for high-exposure sectors at 4°C of warming ($\delta_{high\ exposure}^{4°C,min}$)	0.093025266458601
Sectoral shares of damages in capital stock for low-exposure sectors at 4°C of warming ($\delta_{low\ exposure}^{4°C,min}$)	0.0160184446054674
Additional GFCF due to sea-level rise in sector 5 (mio. 2019-€) ($GFCF_5^{slr}$)	166000
Output loss factor at 4 °C of warming ($X_{loss_1}^{4°C}$)	0.27
Parameter of the function regulating changes in input coefficients in A Matrix ($\beta_{output\ loss}$)	1.107237
Parameter of the function regulating changes in input coefficients in A Matrix ($\beta_{1\ output\ loss}$)	0.153196
Parameter of the function regulating changes in input coefficients in A Matrix ($\beta_{2\ output\ loss}$)	0.054713
Heat-related damage to labor supply ($HD^{Max.Lb}$) at 4 °C of warming	0.24520548
Shares of days with deadly heat pear year at 4 °C of warming	0.49041096
Share of workers affected by deadly heat	0.5
Loss of labor productivity in high-exposure sectors ($\alpha_{Lprod_{high}}$) at 3°C of warming	0.25
Loss of labor productivity in low-exposure sectors ($\alpha_{Lprod_{low}}$) at 3°C of warming	0.18
Total land loss at 4°C of warming (km ²) ($\beta_{SLR, floods, temp, humidity}^{land_loss}$)	4605000
Damage factor on subsistence land intensity ($\beta^{Extra_Int_Land_sub}$)	0.002333333333333333

Suppl. Table 1: Numeric values used in the scenarios with moderate impacts.

2. Main scenario parameters

Variable	Parametrization	Comments
Growth rate in per capita consumption	Center richest class: 0.23% middle class: 0.58% poorest class: 0.86%	We focus on energy- and material-intensive consumption growth rather than on abstract GDP growth. As the material consumption levels of the center are already relatively high, future growth in energy- and material-intensive consumption is
	Semiperiphery richest class: 1.37% middle class: 2.24% poorest class: 2.88 %	
	Periphery richest class: 1.73 %	

	middle class: 2.43% poorest class: 3.00%	<i>assumed to be particularly low.</i>
<i>Energy efficiency</i>	10% improvement in the energy efficiency of economic processes in all sectors until the end of the simulation.	<i>The low growth in material- and energy-intensive consumption is logically linked to a slow improvement in energy efficiencies.</i>
<i>Land intensity</i>	50% reduction in land intensities until the end of the simulation for all land types (agricultural land (cropland and pastures), economically used forest, land classified as 'other land' by the FAO (demanded by the food and the biomass sector), land used for renewable energy generation (water bodies used for hydropower are not considered).	<i>We adopt optimistic assumptions regarding land-use intensities in order to minimize constraints on economic growth stemming from land availability, thereby allowing us to focus on climate damages as potential limiting factor for economic development.</i>
<i>Capital intensity</i>	Increase in capital intensity by 20% until the end of the simulation.	
<i>Electrification</i>	Medium electrification: substitution of 25% of the non-electric energy input by electricity input in all industries and in all final demand components (public consumption, private consumption, gross fixed capital formation).	
<i>Greening of the electricity mix</i>	Reduction of fossil electricity and of nuclear power by 75% until the end of the simulation; substituted by solar PV, hydropower and wind power.	
<i>Energy availability</i>	Medium fossil resource accessibility: all oil and gas resources as well as 40% of the estimated coal resources of the BGR (2020) are assumed to be extractible. Input costs do not increase until all reserves are depleted and increase by 75% by the time all oil and gas resources as well as 10% of all coal resources have been depleted.	
<i>Substitution of fossil energy through biomass-based energy</i>	10% of fossil energy inputs are replaced by bioenergy until the end of the simulation.	
<i>Greenhouse gas (GHG) emission intensity</i>	GHG emission intensity of all economic sectors (including CH ₄ and N ₂ O emissions) reduced by 30% until the end of the simulation.	
<i>Land protection</i>	100% of the primary forest that exists at the start of the simulation is protected.	
<i>Climate sensitivity</i>	High <i>Climate feedbacks within the climate module are activated which lead to additional greenhouse gas emissions from natural systems as temperature rises. The equilibrium climate sensitivity is set to 3 °C.</i>	

Suppl. Table 2: Parametrization of main scenario parameters common to all simulated scenarios.

Supplementary figures

Suppl. Figure 1 displays changes in global average temperature and world output in different scenarios that are characterized by higher growth rates in the center than in the scenarios discussed in the main article. Concretely, the growth rates in per capita consumption are 0.86% for the richest 20% of the center, and 1.37% for the remaining 80% of the population.

Suppl. Figure 1: Scenario results with higher growth rates in the center. a) Change of global average temperature with respect to 1850 in the Baseline (grey), the high-damage (blue), medium-damage (yellow) and low-damage (green) scenarios with endogenously (a) and exogenously (b) evolving labor productivities. World output trajectory in the Baseline, the high-damage, medium-damage and low-damage scenarios with endogenously (c) and exogenously (d) evolving labor productivities.

Suppl. Figure 2: Annual consumption losses for the wealthiest 20% (purple), middle 50% (blue) and poorest 30% (brown) of the center (a & d), the semiperiphery (b & e), and the periphery (c & f) compared to a no-damage scenario. a-c: Scenarios with endogenously evolving labor productivity levels. d-f: Scenarios without endogenously evolving labor productivity levels.

Suppl. Figure 3: Evolution of mortality rates in the center (diamonds), semiperiphery (dots) and periphery (triangles) for different age groups in the baseline scenario (grey) and two damage scenarios (red). a-c) Mortality rates of population aged 10-14, 40-44 and 70-74 in the baseline and in the ABC-type-damage scenario with low impacts and endogenously evolving labor productivities. d-f) Mortality rates of population aged 10-14, 40-44 and 70-74 in the baseline and the ABC-type-damage scenario with high impacts and without endogenously evolving labor productivities.